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THE LINK BETWEEN GENETIC FACTORS IN CHILDREN WITH FEBRILE CONVULSIONS APPEARANCE

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Abstract

The aim of this research paper is to reflect the link between genetic factors and presenting children with febrile convulsions.

Keywords: febrile seizures, genetic factor, the pediatric clinic.

Introduction

Febrile seizures represent the most common problem in pediatric neurology who appear in children from 6 months to 5 years. Cepilae the Commission of epidemiology and prognosis of the International Association for epilepsy seizures febrile defines as an epileptic seizure that occurs after the age of 6 months attached to the disease febrile that are not caused by infections of the central nervous system without the crisis prior neonatal and indiscriminate shared with any other type of acute symptomatic crisis.

There is a vast literature of genetics of febrile convulsions. Based social studies suggest that positive family history is important. Family studies have shown that simple febrile attacks may be inherited in autosomal way, with a dominant big penetrance.

Methodology

The study was conducted at the pediatric clinic of the University Clinical Centre of Kosovo in the pediatric service; the study is retrospective and is conducted between March 2015 in April 1016. In this paper are studied all cases of children with febrile convulsions who have had seizures in the family.

Results

During this period we had a total of 48 cases where the main role was genetic factor that appeared in children are febrile convulsions. The age of children was 6 months to 5 years. 25 cases have been female and 23 male. Age has been affected by it the age of 2 years old. With these results to all children hospitalized with febrile convulsions heritage has been leading role for filing convulsions. During taking a history of the parents of 48 children 17 of them febrile convulsions have inherited from the mother, while 31 others have febrile convulsions they inherited from father.

Conclusions

Pediatric seizures are fairly common in the pediatric age who appear from age 6 months to 5 years, and during our findings we concluded that genetic factor plays an important role in the appearance of convulsions.

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